

Information Quality Assessment of Data Circuit Information for the Arkansas State Network

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Executive Summary

The goal of this project was to identify circuit data quality problems and to recommend solutions to the root causes of the problems identified. Circuit data is a large domain, so the Six Sigma quality methodology was used to help maintain project focus on critical problems with the most impact.

The define phase was primarily concerned with defining the project scope and identifying critical customer needs. The customers, suppliers, information products, and information systems related to circuit information were identified by developing SIPOC diagrams from circuit-related process documentation. Analysis of the SIPOC diagrams and stakeholder interviews were used to determine key problems, information products, and systems on which to focus project activities.

In the measure phase, circuit-related process documentation and information architecture was analyzed and documented. Measurement strategies for key information quality dimensions were also designed and implemented. The accuracy of circuit data was measured using a survey to validate a large sample of circuit data. The representational consistency of circuit data was assessed using a data profiling tool and analysis of pattern frequency statistics. Completeness of the master circuit record was assessed using database queries to identify matching and orphaned circuit records between data sources.

In the analyze phase, results of the measurements were analyzed for root causes and additional measurements were developed. Analysis of the accuracy measurement results identified accuracy defects which were verified and corrected, a process problem which was corrected and mitigated, and a root cause which required additional analysis. Analysis of the representational consistency and completeness measurements identified business rules used to improve cross-system matching criteria. Additional analysis into circuit deactivation lag time was also conducted and used to develop a metric for identifying and correcting additional accuracy defects.

In the improve phase, a circuit ID matching algorithm was developed to improve the completeness of available circuit master records and to help identify additional defects in accuracy and representational consistency. Recommendations were also made for improvements to standards, process documentation, organizational structure, and information architecture that could address the root causes of circuit information quality defects.

In the control phase, metrics were identified to monitor the results of the recommended improvements.

Defects identified and corrected during the project had a monthly defect cost of \$140,152.78 (\$1.68 million annually). The implementation of a matching algorithm for resolving entities across data sources made \$56.6 million in vendor invoice data available for vendor reconciliation activities that can result in vendor credits, reimbursements via federal programs, and use in assessing the quality of additional data quality dimensions.

Background

The Department of Information Systems is the information technology solutions provider for the State of Arkansas. One of the core responsibilities of DIS is the design and management of the state network. The quality of information related to the data circuits that comprise the state network is critical for efficient support and accurate billing of DIS connectivity services. Other DIS processes that rely on circuit information quality include telecommunications vendor invoice reconciliation and the Schools and Libraries Program of the Universal Service Fund (E-Rate).

Suboptimal information quality has been the root cause of past incidents related to both circuit billing and operational support. There has been one large effort in the past to improve the quality of circuit information quality. The scope of that project was primarily focused on identifying and improving the data model for circuit-related asset configuration records in the HEAT incident management system and reconciling any attribute differences in circuit data between HEAT and the MONIES customer billing system. The project resulted in changes to HEAT to improve the relationships between circuit-related asset configuration records and to replace HEAT-specific attributes for circuit termination location and circuit bandwidth with their MONIES counterparts. Since that project, MONIES has been replaced by DIAMONDS as the customer billing system. Additional smaller efforts have sought to address other aspects of circuit data quality in the past but without significant gains.

Assessment of Quality at the Start and End of the Project

This project was largely focused on identifying and assessing the quality of critical circuit information and analyzing the assessment results for potential root causes. Most improvements recommended entail strategic, enterprise-wide changes to organization, processes, and information architecture that would be part of a separate project with a larger cross functional project team. However, during the course of the project, some smaller tactical opportunities for improvement were identified and implemented resulting in the following improvements in information quality.

Accuracy

As part of the project, an accuracy assessment was conducted in which personnel from the serviced circuit locations physically verified the accuracy of a large sample of circuit data. Accuracy defects identified by the assessment were verified and analyzed, and the verified defects were sent to the appropriate groups for correction. Part of the defects identified and corrected were 26 circuit deactivation date defects with a monthly defect cost of \$32,318.75.

Analysis of the accuracy assessment results also led to the development of an assessment technique for detecting accuracy defects in DIAMONDS circuit deactivation dates based on the time lag behind real-world deactivations indicated by vendor invoices. 81 probable circuit deactivation date defects with a monthly defect cost of \$107,834.03 were identified and sent to the appropriate groups for verification and correction.

Only one accuracy assessment was conducted over the course of the project, and only for a sample of the data population, so comprehensive before and after accuracy metrics are unavailable.

Completeness

Analysis of the accuracy assessment results led to the discovery of a process problem that was causing the loss of historical data needed for financial processes. The process was corrected and the lost data was recovered, correcting 59 completeness defects that affected \$717,432.56 in reconciliation and reimbursement data.

The completeness defects identified by the project primarily stemmed from problems with representational consistency that affect the completeness of the master circuit record. A matching algorithm developed during the project did not improve the representational consistency defects themselves, but did mitigate the effects of the defects in order to increase the number of complete circuit records that could be matched across systems. The primary financial impact of this comes from the additional vendor invoice records that were made available for reconciliation and reimbursement processes (Table 1). Identifying the related circuit records between all sources will be critical to the future assessment and correction of additional accuracy, representational consistency, and completeness defects.

	Number of Matching Circuits	Total Vendor Charges for Matching Circuits	Percentage of Total Circuits
Start	481	\$6,076,148	11.76%
End	3,952	\$62,750,806	96.63%
Improvement	3,471	\$56,674,658	84.87%

Table 1 - Vendor Invoice and DIAMONDS Match Completeness Results at Start and End of Project

Description of Project Activities

Methodology

The Six Sigma methodology was used to guide project activities. The Six Sigma methodology has a strong focus on the concept of the “vital few”. In each phase of the process, outputs to the next phase are prioritized and limited to the customers, processes, defects, or root causes that are causing the most impact to the organization. This project covers a large domain, and previous efforts to address the problem have lost momentum and become stalled by ever-expanding scope. I felt that this emphasis on prioritization of objectives would help keep the project focused on the problems that could yield the biggest gains. Six Sigma is designed to be an iterative process, so future projects on the same domain would address the next most important problems.

The Six Sigma DMAIC process has five phases:

- **Define** the problem, customers, customer requirements, and project goals
- **Measure** the current process and collect data for analysis
- **Analyze** the data to determine and prioritize root causes
- **Improve** the current process based on analysis by eliminating root causes of defects
- **Control** the future process to identify future defects and measure improvement effectiveness

This project will place emphasis on the Define, Measure, and Analyze phases. Recommendations for the Improve and Control phase which would require strategic change will be made to project sponsors for possible implementation in a separate project with a larger cross-functional team. Any small tactical improvements will be implemented within the project scope.

Define Phase

The first step in the Six Sigma process is the Define phase. In this phase, a problem is defined, business processes are mapped, customers are identified, and customer needs are assessed.

Project Charter

The overall scope of this project was defined in an initial meeting with the project sponsors. A project charter was then developed and approved in order to define the project goals and boundaries. The key points of the project charter are listed below.

Business Case – The quality of circuit-related data is critical for the accurate billing and efficient support of connectivity services make up 38% of DIS revenue. Deficiencies in circuit data quality are known to have been responsible for problems related to both circuit billing and operational support. Circuit data quality problems also have a negative impact on reimbursement filings for the Schools and Libraries Program of the Universal Service Fund (E-Rate) program, which yields discounts of up to 10 million dollars a year for Arkansas schools and libraries.

Problem Statement - Duplicate entries of many circuit attributes are currently maintained in multiple systems. Some circuit attributes are only found in one of multiple systems, but the relationship information between these circuit records is insufficient to retrieve a master record of all circuit attributes.

Note: The problem statement was based on known problems with circuit data quality based on recent incidents and past improvement efforts, but the project scope allows for definition of additional problems identified through the DMAIC process.

Project Objectives

- Identify circuit data quality problems that impede efficient operational support of circuits and recommend solution(s).
- Identify circuit data quality problems that prevent accurate circuit billing, vendor invoice reconciliation, and E-Rate reimbursement, and recommend solution(s).
- Recommend solutions that demonstrate DIS' technology leadership by using modern, industry-standard solutions to managing data.

Project Scope - The purpose of this project is to define and analyze problems with the quality of circuit data stored in the Helpdesk Expert Automation System (HEAT), DIS Invoicing, Asset Management, Order Notification, Delivery System (DIAMONDS), and the IP Plan IP address management system. Metadata for all circuit data stored in the systems listed will be collected and used to develop a data model of circuit master data. Circuit data quality metrics will be developed and implemented, and recommendations for solutions to circuit data quality problems will be made.

Note: Based on the nature of the known problems with circuit data quality, many of the recommended solutions were expected to involve cross-organizational process improvements or systemic business system improvements. Improvement efforts of this scope and impact should be implemented by a larger cross-functional team as part of separate dedicated projects. Therefore, this project was largely scoped as an analysis phase, which is expected to identify additional improvement phase projects.

Project Authority – The project was authorized by the DIS Director and Chief Operational Officer.

Roles and Responsibilities – I had the primary responsibility for completing all project- related tasks, but additional resources were also named in the charter with responsibilities as subject matter experts.

Critical Success Factors

- Current and potential problems with circuit data quality should be identified.
- The project should result in a data model of all circuit data stored in HEAT, DIAMONDS, and IP Plan.
- Metrics for measuring circuit data quality should be developed and implemented.
- The project should result in a recommended solution to the circuit data quality problems identified.
- The solution(s) recommended should conform to industry best practices for data management.

Defining the Customer

Defining the customer is an important part of the Define phase of the DMAIC process, as the customers of the project may not be readily apparent. The Six Sigma approach is focused on achieving quality through business process improvement, and the customers of each step in a business processes may actually be internal knowledge workers as opposed to external customers.

One tool commonly used in the define phase of the DMAIC process is a SIPOC diagram. A SIPOC diagram is used to identify the suppliers, inputs, process steps, outputs, and customers of a process. I thought that developing a SIPOC diagram for the circuit implementation process would be a good way to determine all of the customers, suppliers, and process steps associated with the information products required to implement and support a circuit.

The traditional SIPOC diagram was found to be suboptimal for my objectives for the following reasons:

- The traditional SIPOC diagram is focused on the process. For the purpose of defining the suppliers, customers, and systems involved in the process, I required more focus on the information products involved in the process.
- The traditional SIPOC diagram differentiates between suppliers and customers at a process level. In the circuit implementation process, the customer of one step can be the supplier in the next. An information product can also have the same supplier and consumer.
- The traditional SIPOC diagram differentiates between inputs and outputs at a process level. In the circuit implementation process, the output of one step can be the input of another step.
- The traditional SIPOC diagram identifies multiple suppliers for a process. I wanted to identify a single supplier for each information product.
- In addition to information defined in a traditional SIPOC diagram, I also needed to define the various information systems or media in which information products are stored or transmitted.
- The traditional SIPOC diagram contains multiple one-to-many relationships, making it difficult to determine the primary customers and suppliers.

Figure 1 - Traditional SIPOC Diagram Format

In order to better meet the needs of this project, I developed a modified version of the SIPOC diagram that is more focused on information products. The key differences are:

- In the modified format, the process becomes the scope of the diagram as opposed to the focus. The focus is instead shifted to the individual information products. This also places more focus on the individual process steps.
- With the focus of the diagram shifted to the information products, the supplier and customers for each individual information product can be more clearly defined.
- The modified format does not distinguish between inputs and outputs. Both are combined as information products as the distinction is not important in this phase. The purpose of the exercise is to identify all information products, suppliers, and customers. The relationships between information products and process steps will be more fully defined during the measure phase, in which detailed process analysis is conducted.
- A block was added for defining the information system or medium in which each information product is stored or transmitted.
- The relationships in the modified format are flat enough to more easily determine the primary customers and suppliers. Steps with multiple customers can be flattened into multiple rows when presented in tabular format without creating any relationships not inherent in the diagram.

Figure 2 - Modified SIPOC Diagram Format for Information Products

The Circuit Request Fulfillment Procedure was chosen as the primary input for the modified SIPOC diagram because it should contain all of the process steps involved in new circuit installations, circuit upgrades, and circuit disconnects. Additional process documentation was also reviewed and used to identify and record any steps missing from the Circuit Request Fulfillment Procedure. An example of the completed SIPOC diagram for one of the processes identified is shown below.

Figure 3 - Modified SIPOC for Circuit Request for Service Process

Initial analysis of the circuit process documentation revealed some inconsistencies and omissions. The quality of the process documentation will be assessed more fully in the measure phase.

Customer Identification

After the SIPOC diagrams were completed, counts of information products were aggregated by their respective customers in order to determine the primary customers for circuit-related information products. While the needs of all customers will be taken into account, the primary customer of the process should have the highest impact on the process.

A Pareto diagram prepared using the data from the SIPOC diagrams revealed that the following groups are customers for 81% of circuit-related information products:

- IP Management
- Network Provisioning
- Network Implementation
- Billing Operations
- Call Center

It was decided to also give emphasis to the following groups based on their financial impact as noted in the project charter:

- Project and Enterprise Program Management Office (PEPMO) (Manage the E-Rate program)
- Vendor Reconciliation

Additional customers of circuit-related information products include:

- Customer (DIS Customer)
- DIS Warehouse
- Installation Vendor
- DIS IT Asset Management (ITAM)
- Telecommunications Vendor (Telco)

Figure 4 - Information Product Count by Customer

Supplier Identification

The suppliers of information products are also key stakeholders, so the same process was used to identify the suppliers of circuit-related information products. The primary suppliers of circuit-related information products were found to include:

- Network Provisioning
- IP Management
- Telco Vendors
- Call Center
- DIS Customer

Additional suppliers of circuit related information products include:

- Installation Vendor
- ITAM
- Network Engineering

Figure 5 - Information Product Count by Supplier

Information Product Identification

14 information products were identified as being involved in the Circuit Request Fulfillment process including the following:

- | | | |
|-----------------------------|----------------------------------|-----------------------------|
| - Circuit ID | - Service Desk Incident | - Customer Equipment |
| - Circuit Installation Date | - IP Information | - Vendor Work Order |
| - Location | - DIS Work Order | - Email Notifications |
| - Customer Profile | - Circuit Request | - Circuit Deactivation Date |
| - Router Configuration | - DIS Equipment Disposition Form | |

Samples of each information product were gathered for analysis in the measure phase.

Information System / Medium Identification

12 information systems or forms of media were identified as being used in the storage or transmission of circuit-related information products:

- | | |
|-------------------|-------------------|
| - Email | - Forms |
| - DIAMONDS | - IP Plan |
| - CA Service Desk | - Remote Routers |
| - HEAT | - Telephone Calls |
| - Core Devices | - Vendor Systems |
| - Cisco Works | - Vital Net |

Customer Requirements

Once the customers of circuit-related information products were identified, interviews were scheduled with key customers in order to determine the needs of the customer, also known in Six Sigma as the “Voice of the Customer”.

Some of the questions asked in interviews include:

- What are the current problems with circuit data?
- What are the known contributors to these problems?
- Which problems are having the most impact?
- What customer circuit-related information is critical to your role?

Some of the key customer problem statements from the customer interviews include:

- Location changes are not always updated in HEAT. This has resulted in dispatching DIS technicians to the wrong site, dispatching vendors to the wrong site at a high hourly rate, and increasing the amount of time required to service sites. (Timeliness, Accuracy)
- The format of circuit IDs is not consistent across sources, which impacts the ability to reconcile circuit inventory with vendor invoices for vendor reconciliation and E-Rate processes.
- Circuits have been disconnected in HEAT but not in DIAMONDS, leading to continued billing for a circuit that is no longer in service.
- Circuits have been disconnected in DIAMONDS but not in HEAT, resulting in an operational support record for a circuit that may no longer exist.
- The Local Education Area (LEA) code used to identify the school in which a circuit is located (part of the location record) is sometimes missing or incorrect, which impacts the E-Rate process.
- Infrastructure circuits are missing from HEAT. During a network outage preceding the interview, technicians did not have all of the circuit IDs available that needed to be restarted. (Completeness)
- The same data elements exist in multiple systems but do not match. (Accuracy, Timeliness, Representational Consistency)
- Often the physical circuit configuration record in HEAT is updated to reflect a disconnect, but not the shared configuration record(s). (Accuracy, Timeliness)

Key critical-to-quality requirements identified in these interviews include:

- Accuracy of circuit termination location
- Representational consistency of circuit ID
- Completeness of circuit master record across all systems
- Completeness of LEA information in DIAMONDS
- Accuracy of LEA information in DIAMONDS
- Accuracy of circuit installation date in both HEAT and DIAMONDS
- Accuracy of circuit deactivation date in both HEAT and DIAMONDS

An additional information product was also identified during customer interviews. Vendor invoices are key inputs to the vendor reconciliation and E-Rate processes, so they will be added to the project scope.

Problem statements

One of the key outputs of the define phase is a problem statement or statements that define which specific problems will be addressed within the scope of the project. The domain for this project is very large, and the problem statements will help focus project activities on the critical few problems identified by customers. If a project attempts to “boil the ocean” by addressing every problem in a given domain, it runs the risk of growing too complex to properly address the primary contributors to process defects.

Based on the requirements identified in the define phase the key problem statements that will be addressed by this project include:

- Circuit locations are not always accurate
- Installation date is not always accurate
- Deactivation date is not always accurate
- Circuit IDs are not always represented in the same format across systems
- Circuit data in one system is sometimes missing in other systems
- LEA data is not always complete in DIAMONDS
- LEA data is not always accurate in DIAMONDS
- Circuit attributes do not always match between systems

Since this project involves a domain that crosses multiple information systems and includes hundreds of attributes, a list of critical-to-quality attributes on which project activities would focus was identified:

- Circuit ID
- Circuit Installation Date
- Circuit Deactivation Date
- Circuit Location Attributes
- LEA Number

Based on the critical-to-quality attributes identified, the focus of the project will be on the following data sources:

- DIAMONDS
 - o The system from which customers are billed and against which vendor invoices are reconciled.
 - o Considered to be the system of record for location and billable inventory.
- Vendor Invoices
 - o Critical input to the E-Rate and vendor reconciliation processes.
 - o An output of the systems of record for the vendors providing connectivity services.
- HEAT
 - o The primary source of information for circuit operational support.
 - o The only known source of reference data about the relationships of circuits, routers, and IP addresses other than the devices themselves.

Note: One of the systems included in the project charter was the IP Plan IP address management system. However, IP address information was not defined as a critical problem to be addressed by this project, so IP Plan was not included in the list of project data sources. Vendor invoices were added as a data source instead due to their relevance to the critical attributes and their financial impact.

Measure

In the Measure phase of Six Sigma, processes are analyzed and documented, key measures are identified, and data collection is planned and executed. Initial estimates for the costs and risks of poor quality information are also identified.

Process Analysis

One of the first steps of the Measure phase is process analysis and documentations. This is important because you must fully understand a process before you can link defects and root causes to process steps and recommend process improvements.

Process Identification

To identify the processes involved with circuit information, the DIS process documentation library was searched for any processes related to the word “circuit”, which were then reviewed for relevancy. All processes owned by the Network Support, ITAM, Invoice Reconciliation or Billing Services groups were also reviewed. The processes identified as being related to the critical-to-quality circuit attributes were:

- Circuit Request Fulfillment Procedure
- Diamonds-Workflow-Circuit WO Entry Procedure
- Diamonds-Workflow-Line-Circuit Procedure
- Diamonds-Workflow-WO Close Process
- E-Rate VRS Procedure
- Equipment and Service Address Standard and Procedure

Process Analysis

The identified processes were analyzed to gain a better understanding of the process and to identify areas for improvement. Key observations from the process documentation analysis include:

- The names used to reference DIS work groups and departments vary across process documentation and the DIS Organizational Chart making it difficult to determine the group to which some responsibilities belong. Updating procedures to use the current group names would make the procedures and responsibilities more understandable.
- The Circuit Request Fulfillment Procedure includes steps related to opening a work order for circuit installations and upgrades, but does not include steps on closing the work order. Billing Operations is listed as being responsible for finalizing the work order in the Responsibilities section of the process, but it is not clear from the procedure how Billing Operations is notified when to finalize the work order. According to the Diamonds-Workflow-Circuit WO Entry Procedure, Network Provisioning releases the work order to Billing Operations after circuit installation is complete. This should be clarified in the Circuit Request Fulfillment Procedure.
- The steps for processing circuit disconnects are included as subset of steps on the Circuit Request Fulfillment Procedure and are not indicated as optional steps in the procedure or flowchart. This makes the installation procedure confusing and may make it difficult for employees to locate the disconnect procedure. The steps for processing a circuit disconnect also appear to be unusually brief (5 steps) compared to the steps required to install a circuit (23 steps). The circuit disconnect procedure may be more clear if separated as its own procedure and documented in greater detail. In the case of circuit upgrades, a circuit disconnect may be related to a circuit installation, but an optional step could be adding referencing the circuit disconnect procedure.

- The DIAMONDS-Workflow Circuit Work Order Entry Procedure goes into great detail on the steps involved in processing a work order for a circuit, but is only related to DIAMONDS work orders and not the other steps involved in provisioning process. The DIAMONDS-Workflow Circuit Work Order Entry Procedure and the Circuit Request Fulfillment Procedure should be updated to include references to each other in the appropriate steps or should be combined into one comprehensive procedure.
- The Equipment and Service Address Standard and Procedure states that “DIS will maintain a single master list of all addresses (in DIAMONDS)” and that “the single DIS address master list in DIAMONDS will be used to maintain equipment and service address information in all DIS applications which contain this information”. Based on statements in customer interviews about equipment address information not matching across systems, it appears that this standard may not be fully implemented or followed.
- No published standard could be identified related to the representation of the Circuit ID attribute. This is a key field for relating circuit records across systems and its format should be standardized and enforced.

Information Architecture Analysis and Documentation

Because this project is focused on information products, the information architecture of the key data sources will need to be analyzed and documented. The key objectives of this analysis are to determine which attributes are stored in each system, how they relate to each, and who the data stewards are for each attribute.

Circuit Enterprise Data Model Creation

In order to analyze the information architecture for circuit data as a whole, an enterprise data model was needed for representing all circuit-related entities and attributes across system boundaries. No such model existed, so one had to be created. This process was started by using the CA Erwin data modeling tool to reverse engineer physical database schemas for each of the data sources identified in the Define phase. These reverse-engineered models provided information on the names, formats, and relationships of all entities and relationships in those systems.

The systems analyzed contained many entities not related to data circuits, so subject matter experts were interviewed to determine the fields in each application in which circuit-related data was stored. These fields were mapped to the corresponding columns in the physical database of each system and used to identify the circuit-related attributes in each of the reverse-engineered data models.

A new logical data model was then created containing the circuit-related entities and attributes from all of the individual systems. Only entities containing at least one circuit-related attribute were included, and only the circuit-related attributes or any key fields required for defining relationships were included for each included entity. Because this was a logical data model, logical entity and attribute names were used instead of physical table and column names.

The HEAT system stores some subtypes in the same physical table. For example, the asset configuration information for circuits, routers, IP addresses, and other assets are all stored in the same table. Each asset type has some attributes that are exclusive to that subtype, but other inclusive attributes are shared across all asset types. To simplify the representation of this, subtypes were broken out and included in the logical data model as separate entities with a subtype relationship to their supertype entity.

All entities from the same system were collocated and systems were identified by labels on subtle outline blocks. Intra-system relationships between entities were brought over from the system-specific data models. Inter-system relationships were defined based on analysis and interviews with subject matter experts. The primary subject area (Customer, Location, etc) was determined for each entity and the entities were color coded based on the subject areas defined.

Analysis of the finished data model resulted in several observations and areas for additional analysis:

- DIAMONDS is supposed to be the system of record for location information, but circuit termination location information is stored in the HEAT Data Circuit Configuration entity.
- None of the HEAT Data Circuit Configuration entities have true primary keys.
- The HEAT Data Circuit Configuration entity has attributes for storing three different types of circuit IDs for up to six circuits on one record. This is because of the one-to-one relationship of a database record with a screen in the HEAT application and the desire to have circuits for one site collocated on the same screen.
- DIAMONDS is the system of record for address information, but there are several sets of address entities in DIAMONDS whose purpose needs to be documented.
- Some customer attributes are stored in both DIAMONDS and HEAT

A list of questions was compiled from analysis of the data model, and a meeting was held with all circuit information stakeholders to identify any missing entities or attributes, define stewardship responsibilities for each data element, discuss location versus contact information, and identify any definition conflicts. In this meeting, the following decisions and recommendations were made:

- The DIAMONDS Building table should be the system of record for asset location information. The owner/steward of this information is the ITAM group.
- Billing Operations should be the data steward of all other DIAMONDS attributes.
- The address fields on the DIAMONDS Account table store the mailing address for invoice distribution.
- The address fields on the DIAMONDS Department table store the mailing address for the department contact person.
- The DIAMONDS User table should be the system of record for circuits (and other billable inventory). Other systems that reference a circuit ID should be constrained to the domain of Circuit IDs found in the DIAMONDS User table. There was some discussion on whether all Circuit IDs (such as backbone circuits) are currently in the DIAMONDS User table.
- The DIAMONDS User table should be the system of record for the circuit Installation Date and Deactivation Date.
- The DIAMONDS Item (Inventory Master) and Transaction Code tables should be the system of record for information about DIS products and services.
- Point-to-point circuits were identified as missing some location information in DIAMONDS because they connect two different sites, but the User table only allows for the specification of the terminating site. Adding an optional originating site Building ID as a user field on the DIAMONDS User table was discussed as a potential solution.
- The APSCN Profile in HEAT was decided upon as the System of Record for LEA (Local Education Area) information.

Note: Since this meeting, CA Service Desk has replaced HEAT as the system of record for incidents. The same customer entities and attributes from HEAT exist in Server Desk and the HEAT customer data was imported into Service Desk. Network asset configuration information remains in HEAT at the time of this writing.

Figure 6 - Circuit Logical Data Model Part 1

Figure 7 - Circuit Logical Data Model Part 2

Measure Group Identification

To begin the process of measure identification, the problem statements identified in the Define phase were broken into logical subgroups based on the related information quality dimension.

Accuracy Dimension

The problems identified as being related to the accuracy dimension are:

- Circuit locations are not always accurate
- Installation date is not always accurate
- Deactivation date is not always accurate
- LEA data is not always accurate in DIAMONDS
- LEA data is not always complete in DIAMONDS

Note: The last problem may appear to be more closely related to the completeness dimension. However, the LEA attribute should only be populated for specific locations (school buildings), so the accuracy of the location key to determining the completeness of the LEA attribute.

Completeness

The problems identified as being related to the completeness dimension are:

- Circuit data in one system is sometimes missing in other systems

Representational Consistency

The problems identified as being related to the representational consistency dimension are:

- Circuit IDs are not always represented in the same format across systems
- Circuit attributes do not always match between systems

Note: Measurements will not be taken for the last problem at this time. A system of record has been identified for the duplicated attributes, and the problem should be addressed through architectural changes, not inspection and correction.

Accuracy Measurement

Data Collection Plan

Previous efforts at improving circuit data quality have measured the completeness of circuit data and attempted to address architectural issues, but no prior efforts have attempted to measure the accuracy of circuit data. This is primarily because of the logistics involved with the number and geographical distribution of the circuit termination points.

During the course of this project, an opportunity to validate the accuracy of a large sample of circuit data presented itself through another project. The Arkansas Department of Education (ADE) requested that I develop a solution to email every school district superintendent a circuit verification form to sign and return as part of the E-Rate process. The form was to include a list of all of the circuits on record for the recipient's district, and each district was supposed to physically verify the circuits listed and sign the form verifying the accuracy of the list.

The circuits used by ADE make up roughly 40% of all circuits provided by DIS. While having verification of the accuracy of such a large sample would be enormously beneficial, I was concerned about getting

back unstructured data related to any discrepancies found. I also saw a rare opportunity to verify the accuracy of other critical-to-quality attributes identified in the measure phase.

I asked ADE for permission to expand the format of the list to include corrections fields for each attribute as well as blank lines for listing any additional circuits found that were not on the list. ADE agreed to this request and a form was designed that included the following attributes:

- District LEA
- District Name
- District Superintendent
- District Street Address
- District City
- District State
- District Zip Code
- District Superintendent Email
- Data or Video Network
- School LEA
- School Name
- Circuit ID
- Circuit Bandwidth
- Circuit Name
- Circuit Street Address
- Circuit City
- Circuit State
- Circuit Zip Code

The form was created using BusinessObjects Desktop Intelligence, a business intelligence tool for querying relational data sources and producing formatted reports. The circuit data included on the report came from DIAMONDS. DIAMONDS stores the school LEA for each circuit as part of the location record, but does not store any of the school district attributes. Attributes related to the school district and superintendent were retrieved from HEAT and linked to DIAMONDS data via the school LEA. Each physical circuit can consist of multiple stations, individual records for each vendor territory it crosses. Only the parent station, the one under which the circuit is billed, was included on the form.

The distribution mechanism requested for this form is called a report burst. A report burst allows for a single report to automatically be refreshed for multiple subsets of data, producing multiple report deliverables, each tailored to an intended recipient. Desktop Intelligence does not natively feature the functionality required to implement a report burst, but it does include a Visual Basic editor that can be used for creating macros using the BusinessObjects Software Development Kit (SDK) to extend the functionality of the tool.

To achieve the intended functionality, I wrote a macro to refresh the report for each school district, save the report in PDF format, and email the report to the district's superintendent along with instructions in the email body and an additional blank attachment for noting additional circuits not listed. The director of the Arkansas Public Schools Computer Network (APSCN) also sent a commissioner's memo out to all district superintendents preceding the distribution of the forms.

In addition to the individual forms, I created a separate report that combined the data from all forms into one large spreadsheet. This spreadsheet was used to determine which forms had been signed and returned and which forms were still outstanding. The sheet included blank columns corresponding to the corrections fields on the forms. As the forms were returned, any corrections were noted in the corresponding fields of the spreadsheet. Additional circuits were added to the spreadsheet as new rows.

This portion of the process did include a manual data entry element. While an electronic form would have been a preferable way to collect the data, the original requirement for the form was to collect signatures, so purely electronic data collection was impractical. Only additions and corrections were

keyed, and the individual forms were retained and used for verifying any changes before corrections were made.

This was a one-time measurement effort, but lessons learned from the process can be used to recommend a more automated recurring process to assess the accuracy of circuit data at regular intervals. This recommendation will not be included in the Improvement phase as inspection, but rather in the Control phase for process verification.

Initial Measurement Results

Once the circuit form data was compiled, some high-level analysis was performed in order to get information for estimating the poor quality information costs related to accuracy defects.

The defects were analyzed and broken out into the following defect types:

- Superintendent Corrections – Corrections to the name or contact information of the school district superintendent. Does not directly affect any financial processes, but can impact operational support and incident management.
- Department Corrections – Corrections to the DIAMONDS Department ID or Department Name. Department is a DIAMONDS entity that directly determines who is billed for a service. It also has a direct impact on E-Rate reimbursement.
- School Corrections – Corrections to the School LEA or School Name. The school or LEA is the entity receiving service. It does not directly impact the billed entity, but it is critical for the E-Rate reimbursement process and for operational support.
- Circuit ID Corrections – Corrections to the Circuit Identifier excluding additions or disconnects. As the natural key for identifying and relating circuit records, Circuit ID has a high impact on every circuit-related process.
- Circuit Address Corrections – Corrections to the termination point of the circuit or location of the router. The circuit address is of vital importance for operational support. While not critical for the generation of an invoice, its accuracy also has financial impact as an asset record and an input to the disconnect process.
- Additions – Any additional circuits reported by districts as being in service but not listed on the verification form.
- Disconnects – Any circuits on the verification form denoted as not being in service at the specified location. Circuits identified as belonging to a different location were not included. Circuits that could not be confirmed due to missing labels or other reasons were not included.

The sample size of the data returned was 1,288 parent circuits. The total population of parent circuits in DIAMONDS is 3,672 circuits, so the sample represents 35.08% of the total population. Based on the sample percentage, defect counts and costs were multiplied by 2.8508 to estimate the defect rate and defect costs for the total population.

Some of the attributes measured are specific to APSCN circuits and do not apply to the entire population of parent circuits. Since the entire population of APSCN circuits was included in the sample, the raw defect counts and costs were used for the population defect rate and costs.

Some attributes have one-to-one relationships with each other such as LEA and School Name. In these cases, the defect count and costs was only reported for one of the attributes to avoid double-counting the impact of the defect.

For defect types with a direct impact on billing or vendor reconciliation, the monthly billing amount was used to estimate the cost of poor quality. Defects resulting in charges to the wrong customer, for the wrong service, or for services no longer being provided can result in credits of the amount billed back to the affected customer but limited options for recouping costs for the lost revenue. To determine monthly billing amount for circuits in DIAMONDS, the circuit ID was used to lookup the billing amount for each circuit. Since the original DIAMONDS circuit ID was not available for the additional circuits reported, the average monthly billing amount of a parent circuit of 839.88 was calculated and used for estimating poor quality information costs.

For defect types related to the school location, the monthly billing amount was used to estimate the cost of poor quality. Location does not have a direct impact on billing, but it does directly impact the E-Rate program which can file for reimbursement for up to 90% of the costs for connectivity based on a discount eligibility matrix. While not all schools are eligible for the full discount, location information also impacts operational support, so the full amount billed was used to as a conservative measure of total impact.

For defect types related only to operational support, defect counts were reported but no defect costs were estimated due to the lack of an objective source for estimating financial impact.

Defect Type	Affects E-Rate	Affects Billing	Affects Operations	Affects Vendor Reconciliation	Sample Defect Count	Estimated Total Population Defect Count	Sample Monthly Defect Cost	Estimated Total Population Monthly Defect Cost	Estimated Monthly Defect Cost Per Circuit
Superintendent Corrections	N	N	Y	N	19	54	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
Department Corrections	Y	Y	Y	N	3	9	\$4,172.25	\$11,894.25	\$3.24
School Corrections	Y	N	Y	N	48	48	\$56,367.96	\$56,367.96	\$43.76
Circuit ID Corrections	Y	Y	Y	Y	304	867	\$334,733.32	\$954,257.75	\$259.87
Bandwidth Corrections	Y	Y	Y	Y	5	14	\$5,158.75	\$14,706.56	\$4.01
Circuit Address Corrections	N	N	Y	N	36	103	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
Additions	Y	Y	Y	Y	73	208	\$61,311.24	\$174,786.08	\$47.60
Disconnects	Y	Y	Y	Y	65	185	\$54,741.50	\$156,057.07	\$42.50

Table 2 - Accuracy Defect Counts and Costs

Representational Consistency Assessments

Data Collection Plan

One of the problems identified in the Define phase was that Circuit IDs were not represented consistently across data sources. This is a problem because the Circuit ID is the natural key for the circuit entity. Inconsistent representation can bypass uniqueness constraints, allowing the existence of duplicate records for the same circuit. Inconsistent representation also impairs the ability to join circuit records across systems for reconciliation and retrieval of a circuit master record.

No published internal standard for Circuit ID format could be found, but all telecommunications vendors use the same circuit ID format, so the assumption was made that an external standard must exist. Internet research indicated that the standard being used by telecommunications vendors for circuit ID representation is the COMMON LANGUAGE Special Service Circuit Codes (CLCI™ S/S Codes) maintained by Telcordia Technologies (formerly Bell communications Research). (http://www.commonlanguage.com/resources/commonlang/productshowroom/product/clci_ss/index.html) Unfortunately, access to the full CLCI S/S standard is only available as a commercial service, so the project did not have access to the official standard or set of valid domain values.

Based on interviews with subject matter experts, the valid pattern for circuit IDs is:
 AAAAAA999999AAAA

Position	Name	Data Type	Definition	Example
1-2	Prefix Code	Alphanumeric	Indicates circuit vendor, exchange, and region	62 = SBC Fort Smith, AR = Alltel
3-4	Service Code	Alphanumeric	Indicates service provided by circuit or circuit type	YG = 56k, YH = T1
5-6	Modifier	Alphanumeric	Provide additional information	FS = Intrastate Tariff Circuit, GK = Interstate Frame Relay
7-12	Serial Number	Numeric	Individual circuit identifier	000432
13-16	Suffix	Alphanumeric	Telco ID	ATI = CenturyTel

Table 3 - Circuit ID Pattern Components

Analysis of sample circuit IDs and the format information above indicates that:

- The minimum valid length for a Circuit ID appears to be 12 characters long. The vendor suffix is variable in length and appears to be redundant to the prefix code.
- The Serial Number does not appear to be globally unique across vendors or even unique to an individual vendor. The serial number 000141 can be found on three different circuits, all for the same vendor. The differentiating code between these three circuits was the Service Code, so the natural key appears to be a compound key including the Prefix Code, Service Code, and Serial Number.

To determine the formats being used by DIS to represent Circuit IDs in DIAMONDS and HEAT and being used by vendors to represent Circuit IDs on vendor invoices, pattern frequency analysis was performed on the active Circuit IDs from each source. The first step in performing the pattern frequency analysis was selection of all active circuit IDs from each data source. All three data sources are relational databases, so SQL queries were written to select the active Circuit IDs from each source.

The active circuits in DIAMONDS were identified by selecting all DIAMONDS Users (recurring inventory records) with a User Type Description of "Circuit" and no Deactivation Date. Both parent and child circuits were included as every station must be supported and reconciled. The total number of active circuits identified in DIAMONDS was 4,550.

Active HEAT circuits were identified by selecting all populated Circuit IDs from the HEAT Configuration table that had a Configuration Type of "Data Circuit", an Installation Type of "Physical", and no Disconnect Date. HEAT stores up to 18 circuit IDs on one physical database record, so each record was broken out into up to 18 logical records depending upon how many Circuit IDs were populated. The total number of active circuits identified in HEAT was 4,700.

Telecommunication vendor invoice data is received in multiple different formats and combined into a Vendor Invoice table in the Billing data mart through automated loads of tapes or XML and manual entry of paper invoices. Active vendor invoice circuits were identified by selecting all distinct Number (Circuit ID or Telephone Number) values for a single Vendor Billing Period (the most recent period for which all invoices were available). Not all vendor charges are for circuits, so telephone numbers were excluded from the query by excluding all Numbers with the patterns ###-###-#### or ##### (the patterns used for telephone numbers). The total number of active vendor invoice circuits identified was 2,164.

The data profiling process was conducted using Talend Open Profiler, an open source data profiling tool. The result sets from the queries above were loaded into new database tables to simplify the profiling process. Talend Open Profiler supports the use of SQL Where clauses on the table being profiled for filtering, but not the complex SQL required to select the data sets needed for analysis.

The new tables were mapped into Open Profiler's metadata repository, and new analyses were set up for each data source. Each analysis was configured to parse the circuit ID data as nominal data and to generate the following:

- Row Count
 - o A simple count of the records in the analysis.
 - o Included because row count must be included in order to get percentages in frequency tables.
- Pattern Frequency Table
 - o Counts the number of records for each of the most frequently appearing patterns.
 - o Replaces all lowercase alphabetic characters by "a", all uppercase alphabetic characters by "A" and all numeric characters by "9". Spaces and special characters are retained.
 - o Includes a bar chart visualizing the frequency distribution
- Pattern Low Frequency Table
 - o Counts the number of records for less frequently appearing patterns.
 - o Displayed the same way as the Pattern Frequency Table
 - o Includes a bar chart visualizing the frequency distribution

The default option of the top 10 patterns was used for the initial analysis in order to find the more frequently occurring patterns and to get samples of the types of low frequency outlier patterns present.

DIAMONDS Results

Figure 8 - DIAMONDS Circuit ID Pattern Frequency Distribution

value	count	%
99AAAA999999AA-99	1175.00	25.82%
99AAAA999999AAA-99	768.00	16.88%
99AAAA999999AAA	698.00	15.34%
99AAAA999999AAA	402.00	8.84%
99AAAA99999999-99	369.00	8.11%
99AAAA99999999AAA	215.00	4.73%
99AAAA999999AAAA	192.00	4.22%
AAAAAA999999AA-99	148.00	3.25%
AAAA999999AAA-99	82.00	1.80%
AAAAAA999999AA	48.00	1.05%

Figure 9 - DIAMONDS Circuit ID Pattern Frequency Statistics

value	count
99.AAA9.999.999-99	1.00
99999999999999-99	1.00
999AA99999AAA-99	1.00
999999999999-99	1.00
99999999	1.00
99.AAA.99.99.99-99	1.00
999999	1.00
999999999999	1.00
99999999	1.00
999999999999	1.00

Figure 10 - DIAMONDS Circuit ID Pattern Low Frequency Statistics

Analysis of the frequency distributions for DIAMONDS Circuit IDs indicated that:

- 5 of the top 10 patterns include a two-digit numeric code preceded by a hyphen at the end of the circuit ID.
 - o This is the Station ID, a numeric code indicating the order in which circuit segments from different vendor territories are linked. Station numbers start with a 01 at the termination point and increment by 1 with each step towards the core router.
 - o It is not unusual to see the Station ID suffix on DIAMONDS circuit ID records, but it was not expected to see the Station ID missing from so many DIAMONDS records.
- 7 of the top 10 patterns match the expected CLCI S/S pattern for the first 12 characters.
 - o The patterns differ in the length of the suffix code (2, 3, or 4 characters), the presence or absence of a Station ID, and whether the prefix codes were alphabetic or numeric.
- Two of the top 10 patterns had a 9 digit all-numeric code in positions 7 through 15.
 - o A six digit numeric code was expected in positions 7-12, but it was expected to have been followed by an alphabetic suffix code.

- Analysis of the record set with this pattern revealed that all circuits with this pattern were Inverse Multiplexing for ATM (IMA) circuits. IMAs are T1 circuits that are bundled together. It appears that in the case of IMA circuits, the same serial number is being used for all circuits in the bundle, and a three digit numeric suffix (001, 002, etc) is being added to the end to differentiate the individual T1s.
- One of the top 10 patterns only had 4 alphabetic characters preceding the serial number instead of the expected 6.
 - Analysis of the record set with this pattern revealed that all circuits with this pattern are DIS-owned backbone circuits that do not service customers directly.
 - Almost all of the circuits in this set begin with the strings “DHDC”, “DHEC”, or “KZET”.

Since the Station ID is a DIAMONDS-specific suffix that is not likely to exist in the other sets and does not appear to be applied consistently within DIAMONDS, the profiling SQL was modified to exclude the Station ID, and the profile was run again.

Figure 11 - DIAMONDS Circuit ID Pattern Frequency Distribution (Excluding Station)

value	count	%
99AAAA999999AA	1874.00	41.19%
99AAAA999999AAA	1171.00	25.74%
99AAAA999999999	370.00	8.13%
99AAAA999999999AAA	218.00	4.79%
99AAAA999999AAAAA	214.00	4.70%
AAAAAA999999AA	196.00	4.31%
AAAA999999AAA	91.00	2.00%
AAAAAA999999AAA	51.00	1.12%
AAAA999999999AAA	41.00	0.90%
AAAAAA999999AAAAA	41.00	0.90%

With the Station excluded from the results, the top 10 patterns all either match the expected CLCI S/S pattern, the IMA pattern with the 9 digit serial number, or the backbone circuit pattern with the serial number beginning in position 5.

Figure 12 - DIAMONDS Circuit ID Pattern Frequency Statistics (Excluding Station)

HEAT Results

Figure 13 - HEAT Circuit ID Pattern Frequency Distribution

value	count	%
99AAAA999999AAA	1216.00	23.95%
99AAAA999999AA	934.00	18.39%
99AAAA999999	782.00	15.40%
99AAAA999999999	429.00	8.45%
9999999999	425.00	8.37%
AAAAAA999999AA	155.00	3.05%
99AAAA999999999AAA	147.00	2.89%
99AAAA999999AAAA	140.00	2.76%
99AAAA999999AA-99	114.00	2.24%
999-999-9999	113.00	2.23%

Figure 14 - HEAT Circuit ID Pattern Frequency Statistics

value	count
AA AAA AAA AAA	1.00
(999)999-9999	1.00
AAAA999999AAA	1.00
999 999-9999	1.00
. 99AAAA999999AAAA	1.00
AAAAAA999999AAAA	1.00
. 9999999999	1.00
99AAAA999999999	1.00
AAAAAAAA AAAAAA	1.00
AAAAAA999999AAA	1.00

Figure 15 - HEAT Circuit ID Pattern Low Frequency Statistics

Analysis of the frequency distributions for HEAT Circuit IDs indicated that:

- 8 of the top 10 patterns match the expected CLCI S/S pattern for the first 12 characters.
 - o The patterns differ in the length of the suffix code and the format (alphabetic or numeric) of the prefix code and service code.
- 2 of the patterns matched the alternate format seen on IMA circuits in DIAMONDS, having a three digit sequential code following the serial number.
- 2 patterns (9999999999 and 999-999-9999) were more consistent with the patterns of phone numbers than with Circuit IDs.
 - o Analysis indicated that these IDs are for Digital Subscriber Line (DSL) circuits. DSL circuits are stored in the HEAT Configuration table, but should be identified with a different Configuration Type, indicating that these circuits had an incorrect configuration type in HEAT.
- At least some Circuit IDs are represented with the DIAMONDS Station at the end, but this appears to be rare.

Vendor Invoice Results

Figure 16 - Vendor Invoice Circuit ID Pattern Frequency Distribution

value	count	%
99AAAA999999AAA	1274.00	58.87%
99AAAA999999AA	434.00	20.06%
99AAAA999999999	286.00	13.22%
AAAAAA999999AA	121.00	5.59%
AAAAAA999999AAA	17.00	0.79%
AAAA 999999	12.00	0.55%
99AAAA999999AA-	6.00	0.28%
AAAA 99999	2.00	N/A
AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA	2.00	N/A
9999 A	2.00	N/A

Figure 17 - Vendor Invoice Circuit ID Pattern Frequency Statistics

value	count
AAAAAAAAAA AAAAA	1.00
AA999999999	1.00
AAAAAA9999999	1.00
AAAA999999AAA	1.00
AAAAAAAAAA AAAAA	1.00
999999999	1.00
AAAAA9999999999	1.00
AAAAAA	1.00
AAAA 99999	2.00
9999 A	2.00

Figure 18 - Vendor Invoice Circuit ID Pattern Low Frequency Statistics

Analysis of the frequency distributions for Vendor Invoice Circuit IDs indicated that:

- There are fewer distinct patterns used for Circuit IDs on vendor invoices that in HEAT or DIAMONDS.
- 98.5% of the circuit IDs on vendor invoices matched the expected CLCI S/S pattern for the first 12 characters.
 - o Like in HEAT and DIAMONDS, the patterns differ in the length of the suffix code and the format (alphabetic or numeric) of the prefix code and service code.
- The pattern with the 9 digit serial number seen on IMA circuits in DIAMONDS and HEAT is also present on the vendor invoices. Analysis of the records with this pattern indicates that the full 9 digits are used for differentiations IMA circuits on vendor invoices.
- The backbone circuits beginning with the DHDC prefix were also present, but with a space in position 5.
- Some additional, unusual patterns were also present, but in extremely low frequencies.

Overall Results

The profiling results from all three data sources revealed that there are three predominant patterns being used to represent circuit IDs prior to the vendor suffix and station number:

- Regular Circuits
 - o 6 character alphanumeric string representing prefix code, service code, and modifiers
 - o 6 digit numeric serial number
- IMA Circuits
 - o 6 character alphanumeric string representing prefix code, service code, and modifiers
 - o 9 digit numeric serial number
- Backbone Circuits
 - o 4 character alphanumeric string representing prefix code, service code, and modifiers
 - o 6 digit numeric serial number
 - o Represented on vendor invoices with a space preceding the serial number

Counts were taken of the number of circuits with each of the predominant patterns identified in each of the three data sources profiled. These counts represent patterns present before any suffix code or Station.

Pattern	DIAMONDS	HEAT	Vendor Invoices
Regular Circuits AAAAAA999999	3,632	3,567	1,852
IMA Circuits AAAAAA9999999999	650	615	286
Backbone Circuits AAAA999999 / AAAA 999999	132	0	12

Table 4 - Common Circuit ID Pattern Counts by Data Source

Analysis of the counts indicates that:

- DIAMONDS and HEAT have approximately the same number of regular circuits and IMA circuits.
- HEAT does not appear to contain the backbone circuits or they are not stored using the same Circuit ID format.
- There are roughly half as many regular and IMA circuits on Vendor Invoices as there are in DIAMONDS and HEAT.
 - o Not all vendor invoices or all lines on vendor invoices may be being loaded or keyed.
 - o There could be a many-to-one relationship between DIAMONDS circuits and Vendor Invoice Circuits, possibly in cases where one circuit must be billed to multiple customers.

Additional knowledge gained from the profiling was that inclusion of the suffix and Station codes cause a great deal of variation in the format of the full circuit ID. These codes do not appear to be part of the natural key for the circuit ID as Station is optional and the vendor suffix is redundant to and less specific than the vendor prefix. For the purposes of matching circuit IDs between systems for checking for duplicate circuit IDs within system, the vendor suffix and station number should be excluded.

It is difficult to accurately estimate the costs of poor quality caused by variation in the representational format of the Circuit ID without further analysis. However, it is known that representational consistency is critical to the ability to join Circuit entity records across systems for reconciliation purposes or for the retrieval of a consolidated record for a circuit.

Completeness Assessments

Data Collection Plan and Results

One of the problems identified in the Define phase was that circuit records can be active in one system but inactive or missing entirely from another system. Every active circuit should have an active record in both HEAT and DIAMONDS since the circuit master record is spread across both systems. Additionally, since circuits are provided by third party telecommunications vendors, every circuit should be receiving a vendor invoice.

To assess the extent to which circuits from one system are missing in another system, the queries developed for the Circuit ID profiling process were used to query DIAMONDS, HEAT, and the Vendor Invoice table. Active DIAMONDS Circuit IDs were joined with active HEAT Circuit IDs and the intersections and exceptions were identified. Active DIAMONDS Circuit IDs were also joined with active Vendor Invoice Circuit IDs to identify the intersections and exceptions. In order to avoid overcomplicating the process, HEAT and Vendor Invoices were not compared to each other directly. DIAMONDS is the system of record, and other sources should reconcile to DIAMONDS.

In order to get a baseline measurement of the current state, all sets were compared using an exact match on the full Circuit ID, including suffixes and station numbers. This gives an idea of compound problem caused by deficiencies in both completeness and representational consistency.

Figure 19 - Circuit ID Intersections and Exceptions (Exact Circuit ID Match)

When the sets are compared using an exact match on the full Circuit ID, fewer than 23% of HEAT circuits match DIAMONDS circuits, and fewer than 18% of Vendor Invoice circuits can be found in DIAMONDS.

The Circuit ID pattern analysis revealed a lot of inconsistency in the representation of Circuit IDs, so some of the exceptions identified when comparing sets with an exact match can be attributed to the formats being used to represent circuit ID.

In an effort to separate completeness defects from representational consistency defects, the sets were compared again, but the match criteria was relaxed by using the following match rules:

- Regular circuits were matched using the first 12 characters of the Circuit ID. This excludes the suffix and Station.
- IMA circuits were matched using the first 15 characters of the Circuit ID. This excludes the suffix and Station.
- Backbone circuits were matched using the first 10 characters of the Circuit ID. This excludes the suffix and Station ID. The space is position 5 was also eliminated from the Vendor Invoice backbone Circuit IDs.

Figure 20 - Circuit ID Intersections and Exceptions (Excluding Suffix and Station)

When the sets were compared excluding the suffix and Station from the match criteria, the number of matches increased dramatically. The percentage of HEAT circuits matching DIAMONDS circuits increased from 23% to 60%. The percentage of Vendor Invoice Circuits matching DIAMONDS increased from 18% to 90%. However, the exception and intersection sets for DIAMONDS no longer summed to the total population of active circuits in DIAMONDS. Also, the number of intersecting circuits from each source no longer matched. This indicates that removing the suffix and Station made the DIAMONDS Circuit IDs less unique, causing many-to-one matches between DIAMONDS and the other data sources. These many-to-one matches introduced 144 duplicate DIAMONDS circuits when compared with HEAT and 32 duplicate DIAMONDS records when compared with Vendor Invoices.

In order to determine if the match criteria had been relaxed too much in excluding the suffix and Station, an additional comparison was performed excluding the Station from the match criteria but not the suffix.

Figure 21 - Circuit ID Intersections (Excluding Station)

Comparing the sets when only excluding only the Station did reduce the number of DIAMONDS duplicates introduced by many-to-one relationships, but it also reduced the number of matches found. The percentage of HEAT circuits matching DIAMONDS circuits decreased from 60% to 50%. The percentage of Vendor Invoice Circuits matching DIAMONDS decreased from 90% to 77%.

Records reviewed during the Circuit ID pattern analysis indicated that suffix codes were not being used or represented consistently across systems, which means that excluding only the Station could exclude valid matches. This is supported by the decrease in intersections seen when suffix was included in the match criteria. However, the decrease in duplicate DIAMONDS records seen when including suffix in the match criteria indicates that cases do exist in which the suffix may differentiate two records. The source of the DIAMONDS duplicates may require additional analysis, but not in this phase.

The potential risks involved or problems indicated by incomplete circuit records include:

- DIAMONDS records missing from HEAT (which may include records that exist but can't be located when needed) can impair operational support and incident management.
- HEAT records missing from DIAMONDS could indicate that:
 - o An asset record is still active in HEAT for a Circuit that has been deactivated in DIAMONDS.
 - o A circuit has been activated and entered into HEAT, but it is not being billed through DIAMONDS.
- Vendor Invoice records that cannot be located in DIAMONDS could mean that:
 - o A vendor is incorrectly charging DIS for a circuit that is not in service.
 - o DIS is not billing the customer for a circuit that is in service.
 - o The Vendor Invoice does correspond to a valid circuit that is in service and active in DIAMONDS, but it can't be reconciled due to differences in Circuit ID. This can directly impact E-Rate reimbursement, which is dependent upon matching Vendor Invoice records to DIAMONDS records.
- DIAMONDS records missing from Vendor Invoices could indicate that:
 - o Vendor invoices have not been loaded or keyed. This can impact the vendor reconciliation and E-Rate processes, which are driven by Vendor Invoice data.
 - o DIS is billing the customer for a circuit that is not in service.
- Any incomplete records make processes less efficient, increasing labor costs.

The costs of operational impact are difficult to quantify, and charges to customers for inactive circuits have already been estimated through the accuracy assessment. The potential impact of invalid vendor charges or missing DIS customer billing can be estimated by summing the billed amounts on the Vendor Invoice records that could not be reconciled to DIAMONDS. The smaller exception set of 220 Vendor Invoices that could not be matched excluding both the suffix and Station were used to calculate the defect costs in order to produce a more conservative estimate. The resulting estimate of the monthly cost of poor quality related to completeness defects was \$267,941.47.

Summary of Defect Costs

The consolidated summary of estimated defect costs identified in the Measure phase is below.

Defect Type	Estimated Defect Count	Estimated Monthly Defect Cost
Inaccurate DIAMONDS Department	9	\$11,894.25
Inaccurate DIAMONDS LEA	48	\$56,367.96
Inaccurate DIAMONDS Circuit ID (User ID)	867	\$954,257.75
Inaccurate DIAMONDS Bandwidth (Item)	14	\$14,706.56
Valid Circuits Missing From DIAMONDS	208	\$174,786.08
Inactive Circuits Active and Billing in DIAMONDS	185	\$156,057.07
Vendor Invoice Circuits Not Found in DIAMONDS	220	\$267,941.47

Table 5 – Summary of Measure Phase Defect Costs

These costs will be further refined with additional analysis in the Analyze phase, but they help determine whether additional analysis is warranted and help prioritize defects to be analyzed.

Analyze

In the Analyze phase, the results of measurements taken in the measure phase are analyzed to identify and prioritize the root causes of any defects discovered. Based on the results of the analysis, the costs and risks of poor quality information are further refined.

Analysis of Accuracy Measurement Results

Additional analysis was first conducted on the data collected for the accuracy assessment. It had the most defects identified by count and cost, and it contained information on probable defects that could be impacting customers and needed to be resolved. The accuracy measurement data also had detailed information available for each defect identified which would be useful for root cause analysis.

The defect data was analyzed by researching the record for each circuit to which corrections were noted. For each record analyzed, the following information was determined and recorded:

- Heat Primary (Termination) Circuit ID
- Heat Associated (Transport) Circuit ID
- DIAMONDS User ID
- Vendor Invoice Circuit ID
- Demarcation Point Label Circuit ID if reported by respondent
- Notes with specific information on defect determined through research

Each change noted by respondents was verified through research, and the changes were color coded to indicate if they were verified as actual defects. Problems in representational consistency were mitigated by using multiple search techniques (fuzzy matching, searches by customer, searches by location, etc) to identify the records for each circuit in all applicable systems. As root causes were identified, they were recorded in a separate document. Verified defects were sent to their respective data stewards in batches for correction.

DIAMONDS Department Defect Analysis

There were only three department defects, so there was not enough data to indicate any root causes. In all three situations, the circuit in question was assigned to the correct School LEA, but was incorrectly coded as a video or data circuit by the DIAMONDS Department.

DIAMONDS LEA, School Name, and Address Defect Analysis

48 corrections to the DIAMONDS School LEA and Name were reported. 14 of the circuits with LEA changes also had address changes, indicating that the schools may have moved. 37 of the 48 (77%) changes were for moves between buildings on the same school campus. 7 corrections involved school name changes but had the same address indicating that the LEA may have changed as part of a merger, consolidation, or annexation.

36 corrections were reported for School Address information. 15 of the corrections were for street number changes only. The rest of the changes were different street addresses.

No root causes could be positively identified, but possible causes include LEA name and address changes not being reported to DIS and LEA changes reported to DIS not being made in all systems.

DIAMONDS Circuit ID Defects

304 corrections to DIAMONDS Circuit ID (User ID) were reported by school district respondents.

In 231 of the 304 corrections reported (76%), the Circuit ID reported by the customer was the transport Circuit ID (Associated ID in HEAT) for the associated parent Circuit ID. Some districts included pictures of their demarcation point labels, and it appears that some circuits are labeled at the demarcation point with a parent Circuit ID, and others are labeled with a transport Circuit ID. Any future circuit verification processes should include both the parent and transport Circuit IDs on the form to assist the customer in identifying the circuit.

4 of the corrections reported were transport circuits that were marked as parent circuits in DIAMONDS, but the parent Circuit ID was on the demarcation point label and reported by the customer.

In 47 of the 304 corrections reported (15%), the Circuit ID reported by the customer matched the Circuit ID in DIAMONDS when the suffix was excluded. This indicates that the vendor suffix is not always used when labeling the demarcation point.

In 14 of the remaining 22 cases, the serial number reported matched the DIAMONDS circuit ID, but there were differences in the modifiers.

While analyzing the results, it was discovered that some of the Circuit IDs from the verification form (which originally came from DIAMONDS), could no longer be located in DIAMONDS. With additional research, it was discovered that the User ID attribute was being updated in DIAMONDS when circuit IDs are changed. This causes the following problems:

- DIAMONDS does not have a mechanism for keeping history, so changing the User ID essentially destroys the historical inventory record of the circuit being changed. This makes the information on the old circuit ID unavailable for processes like ERate and vendor reconciliation which must reconcile historical Vendor Invoice data to DIAMONDS.
- Some attribute values of the old circuit are retained (Activation Date) even though they are not correct for the new circuit ID.

This was a system-specific root cause that could be addressed fairly easily, so the improvement was made immediately while still in the analysis phase. The effects of this practice were communicated to the billing section, and the business process for circuit replacements was changed so that the old circuit record is deactivated and the new circuit is recorded in a separate User record.

In order to mitigate the previous User ID changes in DIAMONDS, subject matter experts were interviewed and historical DIAMONDS data from the data warehouse was analyzed to compile a reference table that can be used to link Circuit IDs that have been deleted from DIAMONDS to the current DIAMONDS User record, which will have the same customer, location, and service information. This reference table contains alias information for 59 circuits and makes \$717,432.56 in Vendor Invoice charges available to the Vendor Reconciliation and E-Rate Reimbursement processes that was previously unavailable.

Circuit Disconnects

65 circuits were reported as no longer in service or not in use at the specified location by respondents. Research into potentially disconnected circuits was conducted by:

- Identifying corresponding records in HEAT and checking for a disconnect date in HEAT or any notes that the router had been returned or that the circuit had been deactivated. If IP information was available, the circuit was also pinged to determine if it was still active. If the circuit was found in HEAT, alternate circuit IDs for transport circuits were noted and compared to the circuits verified as in service by the respondent. HEAT contains the relationships between schools and circuits, so if a match could not be found by circuit ID, a search was performed by school and any alternate representations of the circuit ID noted.
- Identifying the corresponding records in DIAMONDS to determine if the circuit had been disconnected since the verification form was sent out. The full DIAMONDS user ID was recorded.
- Identifying corresponding vendor invoice records to determine if the vendor was still billing for the circuit. If a vendor has stopped billing for a circuit, there is a high probability it is no longer in service. The circuit ID used on the vendor invoice was recorded as well as the last date of vendor billing.

5 of the defects reported were found to be false positives caused by the timing of the verification process. Circuits were still active in DIAMONDS inventory at the time that the verification form was sent out but were deactivated by the time the responses were analyzed.

3 of the circuits were terminating circuits with monthly billing, but no matching vendor invoice or HEAT data could be found. This could be due to representational consistency issues. These were reported to network provisioning for further analysis.

19 of the defects reported were for transport IDs for which no HEAT records or vendor invoices could be located. Transport IDs do not generate actual charges in DIAMONDS, so they do not cause inaccurate billing, but they may represent records for circuits which no longer exist. For some of the records where the related parent (transport) circuit ID was available, the parent circuit ID was found to have been disconnected but the child circuit record left active in DIAMONDS.

12 of the defects reported were found to be due to a lag between the time a circuit is deactivated by the telco vendor and the time the circuit is deactivated in DIAMONDS. The circuits reported had already been deactivated at the customer site but had not yet been deactivated in DIAMONDS. These were different from the false positives caused by timing of the verification process because the circuits were still active in DIAMONDS at the time the responses were analyzed, and the lag time between the physical circuit disconnect and the deactivation of the DIAMONDS record was greater. The monthly amount billed for circuits that were found to have a lag time between physical disconnect and billing deactivation in the sample data set was \$13,734.25.

26 of the defects reported were confirmed as cases where the circuit was disconnected and the telco vendor stopped billing for services, but the DIAMONDS user record was still active. These circuits were sent to network provisioning for additional verification and deactivation. The monthly billing amount for the circuits as being disconnected but not deactivated in DIAMONDS was \$32,318.75.

Missing and lagging circuit deactivations in DIAMONDS appear to be the most costly accuracy defects. It was decided that additional analysis was warranted into possible root causes for these defects.

Circuit Additions

There were 73 additions reported by respondents that were not included on the circuit verification forms. All of these defects were identified as cases where the circuit ID on the demarcation label was the transport Circuit ID (Associated ID in HEAT) for the associated parent Circuit ID.

Analysis of Representational Consistency Assessment Results

Analysis of the results of the representational consistency assessment indicated that completeness may actually be better than the completeness assessment indicated. The number of circuits with each of the predominant circuit patterns is approximately the same in HEAT and DIAMONDS, but only 60% of Circuit IDs match between DIAMONDS and HEAT, even when excluding both the vendor suffix and station from the circuit ID.

In order to better understand the differences in Circuit ID representation between data sources, the actual circuit ID used in DIAMONDS, HEAT, and on vendor invoices was recorded for almost 500 circuit IDs from the accuracy assessment. This data included circuit IDs from different sources that were confirmed to be for the same circuit. Analysis of these circuit IDs indicated that:

- As already observed during the measurement phase, the vendor suffix does not always match between data sources and is not necessary for making the circuit ID unique.
- In some cases, the modifiers in the fifth and sixth positions of the circuit ID are different in different systems for the same circuit. Interviews with subject matter experts indicated that this occurs when the modifiers change but vendors don't update their circuit IDs.
- In some cases, the same circuit ID is used on more than one User ID record in DIAMONDS. In these cases, a sequential number is added to the end of the circuit ID and incremented with each additional User ID. Interviews with subject matter experts revealed that there is a limit to the number of items of service that can be equipped per User in DIAMONDS. When a User requires more than the maximum number of equipped services, a secondary User ID is created to add the equipped items of service that could not be added to the primary User ID. This explains the one-to-many relationships noticed during the completeness assessment. In these cases, the User ID with the lowest sequential suffix should be used when reconciling circuit data with other systems.

These additional business rules could be used to refine the matching criteria used to assess information product completeness and to improve the data available to the ERate and vendor reconciliation processes.

Analysis of Information Product Completeness Assessment Results

Match results obtained during the completeness assessment ranged between 77% and 90% for matches between DIAMONDS and vendor invoices, while match results between DIAMONDS and HEAT only ranged between 50% and 60%. Previous analysis of other assessments suggests that the extremely low completeness assessment results for HEAT are likely due to representational consistency issues and the getting an accurate assessment of HEAT information product completeness will be difficult until representational consistency problems are addressed.

Additional business rules discovered during the representational consistency assessment are likely to improve the DIAMONDS to vendor invoice match percentage above the current 90%, so additional analysis into the relationship between those data sets was not deemed critical. The low completeness assessment results between HEAT and DIAMONDS however, warranted further analysis.

In order to better understand the root causes for HEAT and DIAMONDS circuits that could not be reconciled between sets, both exception sets were analyzed to determine any additional patterns or rules that could be preventing a successful match. Every HEAT circuit configuration record is associated with a HEAT customer profile, and most customer profiles contain the primary key for the associated building location in DIAMONDS. HEAT and DIAMONDS exception circuits were grouped under this location in order to break them into sets of manageable size for analysis. The circuits under each building were then sorted in ascending order in an effort to co-locate possible matches to aid analysis.

DIAMONDS Building Name	HEAT Customer ID	Agency Name
100 Weaver AVE	0710-00096	Department of Human Services
DIAMONDS User ID	HEAT Circuit ID	HEAT Configuration Field
41YHFJ000461001SUV	41HCFS000461001	Primary 1
41YHFJ000461002SUV	41HCFS000461001	Primary 2

Table 6 - HEAT and DIAMONDS Exception Reconciliation Format Sample

Analysis of the HEAT and DIAMONDS exceptions revealed that many of the circuits were actually in both systems, but additional representational consistency problems to those previously discovered were preventing a successful match:

- The station is typically not used in HEAT and is not represented consistently when it is used.
- The vendor suffix is not used consistently in HEAT.
- In addition to different modifiers, HEAT Circuit IDs also appear to sometimes use a different service code for the same Circuit ID.
- Some HEAT Circuit IDs include hyphens, periods, or spaces between Circuit ID segments.
- There appear to be a lot of keying errors in HEAT Circuit IDs indicated by transposed characters, extra 0's and leading or randomly placed spaces.

DIAMONDS Circuit ID	HEAT Circuit ID	Example
41HXFM002094SUV	41XHFM0002094SUV	Transposition and Extra "0"
MEKEFS107411CTE	ME/KEFS/107411/CTE	Slashes
IPLOXX100084WINW	IP-LOXX 10084 WINW	Dashes and Spaces
61LUXX500014SW	61.LUXX.500014.SUV	Periods

Table 7 - Sample Exception Data from HEAT and DIAMONDS Exception Reconciliation

Any Circuit ID matching routines between HEAT would need to strip special characters out the HEAT Circuit ID before attempting a match. The service code may also need to be excluded from the match criteria to successfully match some circuits, but the service code has already been determined to be part of the natural key for some circuit IDs, so this could result in invalid matches.

Grouping the exception sets by location appears to be an effective method for reconciling non-matching Circuit IDs between HEAT and DIAMONDS, and could be a valuable tool for identifying and correcting defective Circuit IDs. However, the process and architecture problems that allowed the defects in the first place should also be resolved.

DIAMONDS Deactivation Date Lag Time Analysis

One of the more costly root causes identified during analysis of the accuracy assessment results, was DIAMONDS circuit deactivations that occur after the physical disconnect of the circuit by the telco vendor. In order to determine the extent of this problem, the lag time between DIAMONDS Disconnect Dates and the last vendor invoice received was analyzed.

All DIAMONDS circuits with a Deactivation Date between 01/01/2007 and 10/31/2010 were identified and matched with the corresponding vendor invoice records. The months between the DIAMONDS Deactivation Date and the last vendor invoice date for the corresponding circuit was calculated to determine lag time. The DIAMONDS monthly billing amount was calculated in order to estimate the monthly cost of lagging circuit deactivations. The DIAMONDS monthly billing amount was multiplied by the absolute number of lag months to estimate the total amount billed during the lag period. Only circuits that could be positively matched between DIAMONDS and a vendor invoice were included in the analysis.

Note: This analysis made use of a matching algorithm described in the Improvement phase for matching vendor invoice circuit records to DIAMONDS circuit records.

The resulting number of deactivated circuits and total billed amount in the lag period was then plotted by the number of lagging months to determine the distribution of deactivated circuits by lag time. The distribution and the details of each deactivated circuit were then analyzed with the assistance of vendor reconciliation subject matter experts.

Figure 22 - Lag Time in Months between Last Vendor Invoice and DIAMONDS Circuit Deactivation

The first step was to determine what constitutes a normal lag time between the DIAMONDS Deactivation Date and the last vendor invoice received. 44.67% of the circuits analyzed had a DIAMONDS deactivation date lag time on -1 months, meaning that the DIAMONDS Deactivation Date preceded the last vendor invoice by one month. This was confirmed as a normal state by the subject matter experts. Circuit billing is typically month-forward, meaning that DIS pays the vendor in advance for the following month's usage. When a circuit is deactivated in the middle of a month, the entire month has already been paid for, so the vendor issues one last invoice the following month with a prorated credit for the unused portion of the month. According to the subject matter experts, a lag time between -3 and 1 months is normal depending on the timing of the circuit deactivation. Circuits with this lag time constitute 72.56% of the result set. In order to identify only the exceptions, circuits with a deactivation lag time between -3 and 1 months were excluded from the results.

When analyzing the detail exception records, the subject matter experts could easily identify actual vendor disconnects when the final amount invoiced was a credit. 79% of the circuits identified in the initial analysis had a positive amount on the final vendor invoice. Depending on the timing of the vendor disconnect and the particular telco vendor, this could represent a valid final vendor invoice. However, it could also indicate that the most recent vendor invoice has not been loaded or that a change to the circuit ID on the most recent vendor invoice may have prevented a positive match. In order to ensure that actual circuit lag times were being analyzed, circuits with a positive final vendor invoice amount were excluded from the results.

The distribution was then updated with the rules discovered to include only the lag time exceptions.

Figure 23 - Lag Time Exceptions in Months between Last Vendor Invoice and DIAMONDS Circuit Deactivation

Analysis of the updated lag time exception distribution indicated that:

- 10 circuits (37%) had a negative lag time, meaning that vendor billing was received for the circuit after DIS stopped billing for the circuit. The estimated cost of these defects is: \$71,551.65
- 17 circuits (63%) had a positive lag time, meaning that DIS stopped billing for the circuit after vendor billing for the circuit had ceased. The estimated cost of these defects is: \$252,099.25

Specific root causes for the lag time exceptions identified could not be determined, but the lack of process documentation for deactivation circuits noted in the process analysis is a likely root cause. The exceptions themselves could have been identified from existing data earlier if not for deficiencies in circuit information quality, specifically the representational consistency of Circuit IDs.

Since this analysis resulted in business rules that be used to reconcile vendor invoice circuit disconnects with DIAMONDS disconnects. The next logical step was to use the same logic to determine any DIAMONDS Deactivation Dates currently missing from DIAMONDS

DIAMONDS Missing Deactivation Date Analysis

In order to identify any current DIAMONDS records that are missing a Deactivation Date, the process used for Deactivation Date Lag Time Analysis was modified to look for DIAMONDS circuits that did not have a Deactivation Date but where the most recent vendor invoice record was received at least 3 months prior to the current date and consisted of a credit. Lag time was based off of the current date.

Figure 24 - Circuits Missing DIAMONDS Deactivation Date by Lag Time in Months behind Last Vendor Invoice

This process identified 81 circuits with a monthly billing amount of \$107,834.03 that have vendor invoice records indicating deactivation greater than or equal to 3 months in the past but have no Deactivation Date in DIAMONDS. The total amount billed for these circuits since their deactivation was \$3,617,386.21. There were two unusual concentrations at the 34 and 37 month marks that seem to indicate mass changes to groups of circuits. These could be false positives caused by a yet unknown business rule. The circuits identified were sent to the Network Provisioning and Vendor Reconciliation Groups for verification and correction.

Analysis Summary

During the analysis phase, the costs and risks of problems were refined and root causes were identified.

Circuit IDs are not always represented in the same format across systems

Problems with the representational consistency of the Circuit ID appear to be a root cause for many of the other problems identified and can impede the assessment of other quality dimensions. The inability to match circuit records between systems can presents risks to the billing, E-Rate, vendor reconciliation, and operational support processes. Matching DIAMONDS records to vendor invoice data is of particular importance. Using current matching techniques, 88.24% of vendor invoices representing almost 64 million dollars in vendor charges cannot be reconciled to DIAMONDS.

Root causes identified for defects in Circuit ID representational consistency include:

- The vendor suffix is not always used
- The Circuit ID modifiers are not always the same
- The Station ID is not always used
- Some HEAT Circuit IDs contain special characters

Deactivation Date is not always accurate

Deactivation date is a critical attribute for accurate billing as it determines when billing stops. 27 instances with estimated defect costs of \$323,650.90 were identified where with the DIAMONDS or the vendor Deactivation Date was lagging behind the physical circuit disconnect. 59 instances with an estimated defect cost of \$3,617,386.21 were identified where the DIAMONDS Deactivation Date appears to be missing for circuits that have been physically deactivated. Instances were also noted where the parent circuit ID was found to have been disconnected but the child circuit record was left active in DIAMONDS. No root causes were positively identified for Deactivation Date accuracy defects, but deficiencies in the process documentation for circuit deactivation are a suspected cause.

Circuit data in one system is sometimes missing in other systems

True defect rates and costs related to circuit record completeness are difficult to determine without first resolving the representational consistency defects that are negatively impacting match results. One root cause identified during analysis for completeness defects that is not related to representational consistency is that User ID (Circuit ID) attribute has been updated on some DIAMONDS records, destroying the historical record. Steps have been taken to prevent this practice in the future and to mitigate the damage caused by past updates.

Improve

In the Improve phase improvements are identified to eliminate the root causes of defects identified in the analysis phase.

Circuit ID Matching Algorithm

Prior to this project, circuit records were joined between data sources using the full Circuit ID, which led to poor matching results. This was a particular problem for the E-Rate process, which must identify all vendor invoices for eligible school and library circuits in DIAMONDS in order to file for reimbursement.

Based on the Circuit ID patterns and business rules discovered during the project, a matching algorithm was designed and implemented to improve the number of vendor invoice records that could be associated with a DIAMONDS record.

Fuzzy Matching

Analysis indicated that several portions of a Circuit ID such as the vendor suffix, stations, and modifiers may be represented differently on different data sources. In order to improve matching results, a fuzzy matching approach was used that ignores certain portions of the Circuit ID when making a match. While fuzzy matching can increase the completeness of the match results, it can also decrease the accuracy of match results. To mitigate this risk, a multi-pass matching technique was used that attempts to make an exact match and slowly relaxes the match criteria if a match is not made.

The following are the matching criteria used in order of application:

- Exact match of full Circuit ID
- Match using first 15 characters of the Circuit ID and the Station ID; match is only made if it results in a single matching record
- Match using first 12 characters of the Circuit ID and the Station ID; match is only made if it results in a single matching record
- Match using first 15 characters of the Circuit ID; match is only made if the DIAMONDS circuit ID has only one Station
- Match using first 12 characters of the Circuit ID; match is only made if the DIAMONDS circuit ID has only one Station
- Match using first 15 characters of the Circuit ID; match is made to the lowest station number in DIAMONDS
- Match using first 12 characters of the Circuit ID; match is made to the lowest station number in DIAMONDS
- Match using the first 15 characters of the circuit ID and the Station ID but ignoring the modifiers
- Match using the first 12 characters of the circuit ID and the Station ID but ignoring the modifiers
- Match using the first 15 characters of the circuit ID but ignoring the modifiers; match is made to the lowest station number in DIAMONDS
- Match using the first 12 characters of the circuit ID but ignoring the modifiers; match is made to the lowest station number in DIAMONDS

During the accuracy assessment analysis, a table was created to store alias information for circuit IDs that had been changed in DIAMONDS. This table is referenced in each step in the matching algorithm. The vendor invoice Circuit ID is first searched for in DIAMONDS. If a match is not found, the same rules are used to search the alias table, which contains the current DIAMONDS Circuit ID.

Algorithm Implementation

The algorithm can be computationally expensive and is too complex for routine use in queries. Also, the logic in the algorithm is continually improved over time, so it was preferred to have the logic in only one place. For these reasons, the algorithm was implemented as a data integration job in IBM DataStage. A column was added to the table that stores vendor invoice data. The DataStage job uses the matching algorithm to identify a matching DIAMONDS record and inserts the records primary key into the vendor invoice table. This DataStage job is called at the end of process that adds new or updates existing data in the vendor invoice table. The new column is indexed as a foreign key to the DIAMONDS user table, so query performance is much better than if the algorithm was included in the query itself. An added benefit of storing the relationship data in a column instead of using the matching algorithm in a query join is that each vendor invoice record can be related to no more than one DIAMONDS record.

Results

In order to measure the effectiveness of the matching algorithm over the previous method of joining circuits across data sources, all vendor invoice records for circuits were joined to DIAMONDS using the full circuit ID, and the each record was classified as matching or not matching. Using the full circuit ID for joining circuit records, 11.76% of the vendor invoice circuit records could be matched to a DIAMONDS circuit record.

Status	Number of Circuits	Total Vendor Charges	Percentage of Circuits
Match	481	\$6,076,148	11.76%
No Match	3,609	\$63,921,590	88.24%

Figure 25 - Vendor Invoice to DIAMONDS Match Results Using Full Circuit ID

The same measurement was taken when using the matching algorithm to join vendor invoice circuit records to DIAMONDS circuit records. Using the matching algorithm, 96.63% of vendor invoice circuit records were matched to a DIAMONDS circuit record.

Status	Number of Circuits	Total Vendor Charges	Percentage of Circuits
Match	3,952	\$62,750,806	96.63%
No Match	138	\$7,246,932	3.37%

Figure 26 - Vendor Invoice to DIAMONDS Match Results Using Matching Algorithm

The matching algorithm identified matches for an additional 3,471 circuits and an additional \$56,674,658 in vendor charges over matches made using the full circuit ID. This raw match percentage increased by 84.87% of the whole (a 721.62% increase in matches).

Status	Number of Circuits	Total Vendor Charges	Percentage of Circuits
Improvement	3,471	\$56,674,658	84.87%

Figure 27 - Matching Algorithm Improvement over Full Circuit ID Match

While it is preferable that a standard for representation of Circuit IDs be created and implemented to ensure representational consistency at the source, the matching algorithm will help optimize circuit matching results until a standard can be put into effect. The algorithm will also be instrumental in identifying Circuit IDs that are not in compliance with the standard and must be corrected.

The matching algorithm has currently not been implemented for matches between DIAMONDS and HEAT. By the time the improve phase of the project had begun, a new incident management system named Service Desk had begun replacing HEAT. Service Desk is designed solely for incident management and is not intended to store asset configuration data. Asset configuration data is currently still being maintained in HEAT, but a new system of record will need to be determined or developed for network asset configuration data.

Recommended Standards Improvements

Defects in the representational consistency of Circuit IDs appear to be a root cause to nearly every circuit-related defect. Circuit ID is one of the most critical data elements in the organization, yet it has no published format standard. It is highly recommended that a standard for the representation of Circuit IDs be developed, published, and enforced. An external standard already exists that is being used by telco vendors which should keep vendor representation of circuit IDs fairly consistent. Since the vendor representation of Circuit IDs must be used when communicating with vendors on operational and financial matters, it would make sense to conform the internal representation of Circuit IDs to the format being used by the circuit vendor.

Recommended Process Documentation Improvements

The quality of the processes used to create and maintain information is critical to the quality of the information produced. Based on an assessment of the processes used to create and maintain circuit-related information, there are several recommended areas for improvement:

- Organizational group names should be standardized and updated in the process documentation.
- The multiple procedures that comprise the circuit implementation process should reference each other or be combined so that a complete view of the circuit implementation process is easily identifiable. Some steps appear to be missing when responsibilities cross organizational boundaries, and cross-referencing or combining the procedures may help.
- Based on the number of circuit disconnects that were not processed in DIAMONDS, the process documentation for disconnects needs to be improved. It is currently part of the circuit implementation process documentation, which adds confusion to both processes. It also appears to be unusually brief compared to the circuit implementation process. Separate process documentation for disconnects should be created to focus and elaborate on the process.

Recommended Organizational Improvements

A lot of the root causes of circuit data quality problems stem from a siloed approach to data management. Individual organizational units implement information systems to address their own needs, often creating multiple unintegrated copies of enterprise data.

A centralized data governance program is recommended to improve the management of critical enterprise data. A core data governance council should be chaired and championed by a C-Level leader and staffed with representatives of both technical and business units.

The core goals of the data governance council should be to:

- Identify mission-critical information products along with their suppliers, systems, and customers
- Identify a single system of record for each information product
- Appoint a single data steward for each information product
- Disallow changes to information products outside of their system of record
- Evaluate the current information architecture and design an optimized future state and gap plan

Recommended Information Architecture Improvements

Data governance is primarily implemented through communication, policies, and procedures, but the enterprise information architecture will likely require changes in order to support and enforce decisions made by the data governance council.

Information architecture improvements recommended to improve circuit information quality include:

- The network asset configuration information currently stored in HEAT will need to be relocated before the HEAT system goes offline. The new system of record:
 - o Should not allow direct modification of any attributes that have another system of record
 - o Should contain relationships to allow discovery tools to be used to verify network inventory
- DIAMONDS was determined to be the system of record for the Circuit ID attribute. All other systems should restrict entry of Circuit ID to the valid domain of Circuit IDs in DIAMONDS.
- Controls should be put in place to enforce business rules and detect business rule violations.

To assist with making data available to systems of reference, a master data hub should be considered. DIS already owns many enterprise licenses of Microsoft SQL Server, and Microsoft Master Data Services is included with a SQL Server license starting with version 2008 R2. Implementing an MDM tool like Master Data Services can help centralize management of master data, expose master data to systems of record, and keep history of changes to master data. Enforcement of business rules and the detection and notification of business rule violations are also supported by MDM tools.

Control

In the Control phase, a monitoring plan is designed and implemented to determine if improvements are achieving the desired results and if the process is holding the performance gains.

Completeness Controls

The HEAT and DIAMONDS Circuit Reconciliation Report developed during the analysis phase scheduled for weekly distribution to the Network Implementation group for analysis and correction.

Representational Consistency Controls

Once a Circuit ID format standard is developed and published, an exception reporting process should be developed to distribute reports of Circuit IDs that are in violation of the standard.

Accuracy Controls

Accuracy can be difficult to measure on a regular basis because confirming the accuracy of an attribute usually requires validating it against a physical object. Circuits are numerous and geographically dispersed, so taking a physical inventory can be costly and time consuming.

However, telco vendor invoices can provide some degree of third party validation for some attributes, particularly those related to circuit installation and deactivation. Lagging circuit deactivations in DIAMONDS have been determined to be a problem, and vendor invoice deactivations appear to be a valid method of detecting circuit deactivations in the physical world. An exception reporting process should be developed to distribute lagging DIAMONDS circuit deactivations to the Network Provisioning group for analysis and possible correction.

Conclusion

The primary problems with the quality circuit information identified by the project are the representational consistency of circuit IDs, the accuracy of circuit deactivation dates, and accuracy of circuit location data.

The representational consistency of circuit IDs is critical to the ability to reconcile circuit data across systems to retrieve a master record, to accurately identify circuits when contacting telco vendors to resolve operational issues, and for identifying vendor invoice charges for reconciliation and reimbursement activities. The inability to match records across system also impairs efforts to measure, analyze, and improve other information quality metrics because attributes cannot be compare across systems.

82% of vendor invoice circuits do not match the circuit ID in DIAMONDS when using an exact match. A fuzzy matching algorithm was used to dramatically improve the match rate, but even with the algorithm 15% of vendor invoice circuits cannot be reconciled to DIAMONDS. The primary root cause identified for problems with the representation consistency of circuit IDs is the lack of a published internal standard for the representation of circuit ID. It is recommended that a standard be developed and enforced through information architecture constraints and monitoring processes.

The most costly problem identified was defects in the accuracy of circuit deactivation dates. Lagging or missing circuit deactivation dates in DIAMONDS can result in inaccurate customer billing and poses risks for filing inaccurate Erate reimbursement requests, which can result in the loss of Erate funding. 26 out of the 1,288 circuits included in the accuracy assessment sample (2%) had a missing deactivation date in DIAMONDS, resulting in monthly billing errors of \$32,318.75. Additional analysis based on DIAMONDS deactivation dates compared to vendor invoice deactivations identified 81 (1.7%) disconnected circuits with missing deactivation dates in DIAMONDS and monthly billing errors of \$107,834.03.

The primary root causes identified for accuracy defects in circuit deactivation dates were deficiencies in process documentation and the lack of information architecture constraints to share information across groups and systems. Process documentation, information architecture improvements, and control measures were recommended to address the root causes identified.

84 of the 1,288 included in the accuracy assessment sample (6.5%) had problems with attributes related to the location of the circuit termination point. Defects in location information can impede the operational support of circuits as well as the Erate reimbursement process. No definite root cause was identified, but possible causes could be location changes not reported by the customer and location changes not communicated across internal divisions. Recommended information architecture changes to eliminate the maintenance of redundant attributes in multiple systems could help address this problem.

Most of the root causes identified by this project could be mitigated or prevented through an enterprise-level data governance program and the information architecture changes to support data governance policies. A data governance program is highly recommended and would likely address additional or prevent additional information quality problems as well as those identified by this project.